

Immersion Approach and Technological Skills of Grade Two Learners

Maria Carla B. Daradar

Abstract. This study seeks to determine the level of Technological Skills of the learners. Eventually, it also seeks to determine the magnitude of effect of the Immersion Approach on the Technological Skills of Grade Two Learners. This study was conducted in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, Division of Davao del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 60 grade two learners – 34 were from section A which were the controlled group and 26 were from section B which were the experimental group. The composition of these two sections was homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B had identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. Moreover, the experiment was conducted based on the mechanics of Immersion Approach. This study was conducted in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, Division of Davao del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 60 grade two learners – 34 were from section A which were the controlled group and 26 were from section B which were the experimental group. The composition of these two sections was homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B had identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. Moreover, the experiment was conducted based on the mechanics of Immersion Approach. This study revealed that immersion approach has an effect on the technological skills of grade two learners. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

KEY WORDS

1. Immersion Approach 2. Technological Skills 3. Grade Two Learners

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1. Introduction

Immersion education is a teaching method where students learn all subjects in a target language. Teacher who are fluent and native speakers of the target language, commit to speaking it consistently. They use the target language during instruction, transitions, outdoor play, and meal times. Teachers pay close attention to students' needs and individual learning styles (Alamri et.al., 2020). The classroom features a literacy-rich environment with pictures, labels, and meaningful visuals to support the target language throughout the day. Teachers adeptly help comprehension through non-verbal clues and smart teaching strategies. Children make connections across the curriculum as the target language and English curriculum align, reinforcing concepts and ideas in both languages (Jackson, 2021). Immersion also includes more elements

of discovery- and inquiry-based learning than do other kinds of instructional practices. Students must constantly and consistently decipher inferences and context clues. Research indicates that children in immersion settings perform the same or better than their non-immersion peers (Brondum and Stenson, 2023). Technology in education is changing at a faster pace than ever before. From the turn of the millennium, digital technology has been growing in prevalence within education, and it's not just about computers. The early 2000s saw interactive whiteboards introduced. We've since seen a wide range of technology make its way into education – from portable and handheld devices in the 2010s to increasingly sophisticated software for learners and educators (Fearnley and Amora, 2020). Technology has a positive impact on student engagement, according to research. It can help educators create exciting, engaging and memorable lessons. Needless to say, higher engagement makes pupils more motivated and makes lessons more enjoyable for both students

and teachers. The use of technology in education can truly grab students' attention (Mahande and Akram, 2021). While traditional teaching methods are typically effective at engaging some students in a classroom, integrating edtech into their pedagogy can help educators engage every student in the class. Additionally, digital learning helps students improve those invaluable digital skills which are fundamental in modern life. While today's learners are naturally proficient with technology like smart phones and computers, using them in an education setting throughout K-12 will familiarize them with more practical applications (Leelakulthanit, 2022). In the Division of Davao del Sur particularly in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School the same problem is encountered on poor technological skill proficiency of the learners, the researcher being a teacher in the primary grade explores to determine the effect immersion approach on the technological skills of grade six learners. Hence, this study.

2. Methodology

This chapter discussed the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study made use of the quasi experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design was a good design when the researcher had access to

one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study were intact group of learners. This design was represented as follows:

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, Division of Davao del Sur. The subjects of this study were the 60 grade two learners – 34 were from section A which were the controlled group and 26 were from section B which were the experimental group. The

composition of these two sections was homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B had identical grades. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study. Moreover, the experiment was conducted based on the mechanics of Immersion Approach.

0₁ x 0₂

0₃ x 0₄

Where:

- 0₁ - Pretest of the experimental group
- 0₂ - Posttest of the experimental group
- 0₃ - Pretest of the controlled group
- 0₄ - Posttest of the controlled group
- - Non-random assignment of subjects
- X - Treatment applied in the experimental group

Distribution of Respondents

	Subjects	No. of Pupils
1	Section A	34
2	Section B	26
	Total	60

2.3. *Research Instrument*—The research instrument in this study was researcher -made which focused on the technological skills of the grade two learners. The researcher prepared a performance task that will be graded based on the rating system of DepEd. The pre and post-performance test consist of a 25 –item test eventually determined the technological performance of the research subjects. The pretest was

administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest was very helpful to assess the effect of immersion approach on the technological skills of the grade two learners. On the other hand, post test was administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the effect of immersion approach on the technological skills of grade two learners, the following continuum was used based on DepEd rating system.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher drafted a letter seeking for permission that this research study be conducted were sent to the Schools Division Superintendent in the division of Davao Del Sur and to the school principal concerned. While letters seeking for permission were delivered to the DepED Schools Division Superintendent, Dr. Nelson C. Lopez, CESO V and to the principal of Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the experts of the

study. After permission had been granted that this study be conducted in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School and after the research questionnaire had been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher administered pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commenced her experiment in the experimental class. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher administered posttest to both sections. Scores of the subjects were submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher made analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and inter-

pretation the responses in this study. Mean was used to describe the technological skills of

Interval Scale and Performance Levels

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings and, and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings, but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

the subjects from controlled and experimental groups in pretest and posttest. t-test for uncorrelated samples was used to test the significance of difference between the pretest and posttest

mean scores in the experimental and controlled groups. Eta square was used to measure the magnitude of effect of immersion approach on the technological skills of learners

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

Pre-Test Score of Learners Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade two learners. The controlled group got the mean of 32.55 with a

rating of 72.33 or Beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 31.31 with a rating of 69.57 or Beginning.

Table 1. Pre-Test Score of Pupils

	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Pre-test	34	32.55	72.33	Beginning
Experimental Group				
Pre-test	26	31.31	69.57	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the controlled group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs Beginning level. This means that learners both controlled and experimental groups are still struggling to acquire basic skills in technology. Immersion education is a teaching method where students learn all subjects in a target language. Teachers who are fluent and native speakers of the target language, commit to speaking it consistently. They use the target language during instruction, transitions, outdoor play, and meal times. Teachers pay close attention to students' needs and individual learning styles (Alamri et.al., 2020). The classroom features a literacy-rich environment with pictures, labels, and meaningful visuals to support the target language throughout the day. Teachers adeptly help comprehension through non-verbal

clues and smart teaching strategies. Children make connections across the curriculum as the target language and English curriculum align, reinforcing concepts and ideas in both language (Jackson, 2021).

Post-Test Score of Pupils

Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the grade two learners. The controlled group got the mean of 36.76 with a rating of 81.68 or Approaching Proficiency while the experimental group gained the mean of 42.25 with a rating of 93.88 or Approaching Proficiency. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 24.31 from a mean rating of 69.57 to 93.88. This means that the student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, and can

transfer them independently through authentic performance task. This also means that experiential group has a far better performance than the controlled group.

Table 2. Post-Test Score of Pupils

	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Post-test	34	36.76	81.68	Approaching Proficiency
Experimental Group				
Post-test	26	42.25	93.88	Proficient

Immersion also includes more elements of discovery- and inquiry-based learning than do other kinds of instructional practices. Students must constantly and consistently decipher inferences and context clues. Research indicates that children in immersion settings perform the same or better than their non-immersion peers (Brondum and Stenson, 2023). Technology in education is changing at a faster pace than ever before. From the turn of the millennium, digital technology has been growing in prevalence within education, and it's not just about computers. The early 2000s saw interactive whiteboards introduced. We've since seen a wide range of technology make its way into educa-

tion – from portable and handheld devices in the 2010s to increasingly sophisticated software for learners and educators (Fearnley and Amora, 2020). Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score.

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -5.32 with a p-value of .0211 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest scores and the post test scores of the grade two learners. This implies that the used immersion approach has increased the technological skills of the grade two learners.

Table 3. Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	39	-5.32	.0211	Significant

Technology has a positive impact on student engagement, according to research. It can help educators create exciting, engaging and memorable lessons. Needless to say, higher engagement makes pupils more motivated and makes lessons more enjoyable for both students and teachers. The use of technology in education can truly grab students' attention (Mahande and Akram, 2021). While traditional teaching methods are typically effective at engaging some

students in a classroom, integrating edtech into their pedagogy can help educators engage every student in the class. Additionally, digital learning helps students improve those invaluable digital skills which are fundamental in modern life. While today's learners are naturally proficient with technology like smart phones and computers, using them in an education setting throughout K-12 will familiarize them with more practical applications (Leelakulthanit, 2022).

Table 4. Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Grade Two Learners

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
42	-4.22	0.378	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Table 4 highlights the test of immersion Approach and its effect on the technological skills of grade two learners. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.378 which signifies large effect. This implies that the used of Hire a Resource Person Approach develops the industrial arts skills of the grade two learners. This finding is in conjunction with the statement of Cummins (2020) who said that many research findings show many benefits for students in immersion learning pro-

grams. The most widely investigated topic in regards to language immersion students is performance on standardized testing. Ultimately, research reveals that students in immersion programs perform as well as, if not better than, students without immersion background. This is good news for immersion proponents, as previous research indicated a gap in performance from immersion students (Cummins, 2020).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made.

4.1. *Findings*—This study sought to determine the effect of Immersion Approach and technological skills of grade two learners. This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study was conducted in Sta. Cruz Central Elementary School, Sta. Cruz South District. The subjects of this study were the 60 grade two pupils – 34 are from section A which comprised the controlled group and 26 are from section B composed the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is heterogeneous therefore pupils of sections A and B have identical range of performance. This study made use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B were involved as subjects of the study.

This study revealed that immersion approach has an effect on the technological skills of grade two learners. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.2. *Conclusions*—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade two learners both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group is at the Approaching Proficiency while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Advanced level.

4.3. *Recommendations*—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers should integrate technology in his classroom instruction. On the other hand, in order for learners to learn technology used in the classroom there is a need to immerse these learners in technology.

If learners have technological skill, it is easier for them to learn the technology-aided lesson, thus learning happens. The school heads should support the initiative of the teachers especially if it gears to develop skills or competence of the learners. Further, the school head should motivate other teachers to duplicate any school initiatives of other teachers which are product of a research study. Every teacher should be technology literate in order to produce learners who are literate in technology. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the technological skills of learners addressing other variables will be conducted.

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